

COMPATIBILITY OF INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCE AND MODERN PEDAGOGY IN LANGUAGE EDUCATION

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Abstract. *This article presents the functional exchange in language education, emerging concepts in the field of modern pedagogy and their essence, by providing particular thoughts on the criteria of test tasks used to monitor students' knowledge.*

Keywords: *international studies, Bloom's taxonomy, Paul's taxonomy, small, large, mixed, complex texts, criterion-normative testing, ipsative testing, empathy.*

It is important to suggest that the concept of reading literacy has been activated in the education system along with the preparation for international studies. This is similar to a "paradigm shift", that is, an object that was previously focused on from one point of view is now encouraged to analyze it from another point of view. A paradigm shift has also occurred in mother tongue education. Whereas previously we relied on the grammar approach to language teaching, today a competency-based approach, integration of subjects and the goal of preparing students for life have entered language education.

According to Bloom's taxonomy, the goal of learning consists of "knowledge, understanding, application, analysis, synthesis and evaluation". In this case, taxonomy means a theory of classification and systematization of complexly structured spheres of existence" [1]. The use of this taxonomy in the educational process is compatible with the stages of working on the text of assignments.

Because at the stages of working with the text of international studies, the conditions for understanding, evaluation and reasoning, assessing the quality and reliability of the text, reflecting on the form and content of the text, identifying and eliminating deficiencies are set. In this case, the processes of understanding, analyzing, synthesizing and evaluating the taxonomy are mutually compatible.

Table 1. Compatibility of reading literacy testing with methodological models.

T	The process of working on a text in PISA		Bloom's taxonomy	
	Structure	Content	Structure	Content
1	Understanding.	Describing the meaning in memory, drawing a conclusion.	Knowledge	Memorization of theoretical knowledge in the form in which it was taught.
2	Evaluation and reasoning	Must understand the figurative meaning of the text, different from the literal meaning	Understanding.	Transfer to another situation corresponding to the real situation, interpretation.

3	Text quality and reliability	Evaluate whether the information is reliable, up-to-date, correct, or not abstract	Application	Solve problems using previously known principles and generalizations.
4	Text form and reflection on content	The content of the text should be connected with knowledge outside the text		Analysis determine the characteristics of the components, and determine the relationships between the individual parts.
5	Identifying and eliminating deficiencies	The student resolves a conflict in several texts that have contradictory meanings.	Synthesis	Gathering, proving, creatively approaching learned information and solutions, and solving problems.
6			Evaluation	Making judgments based on clear data, applying logic and philosophy

What is more important, after Bloom's taxonomy, Paul's taxonomy was proposed. The stages were divided into "remembering, understanding, applying, analyzing, evaluating, and creating" [2]. The main indicator is visible when it is presented before the evaluation stage.

It is believed that students are able to innovate only after they prove their judgments and evaluate them. It should be said that when comparing knowledge, understanding in Bloom's taxonomy and remembering, understanding in Paul's taxonomy, the second stages of the taxonomy have a deeper meaning, that is, it can be seen in the levels of lexical meaning of the words understood and comprehended.

In addition, in pedagogical and methodological works, preference is given to the "5E" model [3]. 5E is an abbreviation of the English words "attract", "explore", "explain", "develop", "evaluate". It means attracting, teaching, explaining, developing and evaluating respectively. It can be seen that learning practical skills through these processes correlates with the essence of Bloom's and Paul's taxonomies. Understanding is the beginning of any scientific process. Without understanding a text or source, it is impossible to evaluate or judge it. It is necessary to read carefully in order to understand the text.

After reading and understanding the text, the student automatically evaluates the text. It is through this evaluation process that students can reflect. Texts are diverse, and its quality and reliability are based on the specific facts presented in the text and the accuracy of these facts. In philosophy, there is a concept of form and content, and later this concept entered almost all fields. The form and content of the text itself must be mutually consistent.

In the process of working with texts, students also identify its shortcomings and think about how to eliminate them.

Table 2. Classification of text types by text format, given in international studies

T/r	Text Type	Features related to working with text types	Scope of application
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1	Large texts	Contains a number of paragraphs. Information is formatted using italics or bold, line boxes and style, and different fonts, sizes, and typefaces. Introductory words are used. With the help of auxiliary means, such as first, second, and modal words, for example, because, therefore, the content of the text expresses cause-and-effect relationships.	Articles, letters, stories and essays, newspaper news
2	A small text may consist of a single heading line, but may also consist of several linked sub-headings.	Such texts represent statistical and active data and are in most cases updated via the Internet.	Tables, graphic texts, diagrams, advertisements, lesson plans, catalogs.
3	Mixed texts	Include static and active, large and small formats, and simple and clear texts. Usually, such texts need to explain changes in diagrams, discuss changes in information in graphic form with the help of appropriate instructions. Journals, references and statements.	For example, a descriptive paragraph, a logically connected text containing explanatory and conditional symbols are mixed texts.
4	Complex texts	Internet and informational texts, such as e-mails and forums, consist of both large and small format texts.	This type of text is now also called "source" text. Authored texts based on data, both large and small formats, enriched with images.

Definitely, introducing work on the above-mentioned types of texts into teaching the native language has a number of advantages. Firstly, working on a large-scale text develops students' ability to understand texts of any field, subject and content. Thanks to this, students will have a number of opportunities to choose a profession in the future. Therefore, the goal of school education is to ensure employment of young people in the future. According to A. Shlyakher, education is the only way to get rid of poverty. This type of text corresponds to the text "Supreme Assembly" in the textbook for grades 7.

Most of the texts presented in the textbook for grades 6-7-8 are small texts and are important for developing students' social competence. Understanding mixed and complex texts requires students to be intelligent. At the same time, the student thinks independently, learns to independently express their decisions, thinking accelerates in the process of analysis and synthesis. Quick thinking is not a quick solution to problems. R. Stefan also condemned this situation. It is important to complete the task by deeply reflecting on the root of the problem. It is mixed and complex mats that develop these skills in students.

Besides that, the presence of computer assessment in international studies requires the use of adapted tests in the assessment process. The peculiarity of this type of test is that it gives fewer tasks in the process and makes it possible to assess students' thinking at a high level. At the same time, tasks are given taking into account the capabilities and abilities of students. Adapted tests are even more useful for assessing less capable students. Because it is necessary to explain only the concepts present in the options.

Working with texts is the basis of modern international studies. Whether it is mathematics or natural sciences, the basis of each of them is reading comprehension. Given that international studies are inextricably linked with testing, textbooks must include aspects that should be determined before testing. That is, we need to develop tasks that answer students' questions about which areas or structures should be measured, for what purpose and whether the form of assessment we have chosen can measure the skills we expect.

According to the methodology for analyzing the results of tasks, all tests are divided into three groups. It is divided into a group of standards, non-standard and ipsative tests" [4]. This section reveals the way of studying international studies. That is, the results of students who have completed standardized tests are compared.

In assessment programs, the results of students of a certain age are compared. It is advisable to use standardized tests in textbooks. Because these types of tasks measure information that students need to know. By comparing the results obtained from year to year, it is possible to identify shortcomings and develop measures to eliminate them. In this case, ipsative tests are important. To achieve effective results in international studies, it is better to use different criteria for test tasks. Tasks included in the new curriculum and textbooks should be completed based on the testing criteria.

Table 3. Domains considered in international studies

T/r	Domain	Importance of Domain
1	Reading literacy	Development of students' knowledge and skills to use, process, reflect and understand a variety of information
2	Mathematical literacy	the ability to think mathematically about various life situations and problems, express a given task using mathematics, use mathematics to solve the task, and use the results obtained to interpret and evaluate the solution to the task
3	Science Literacy	Knowledge of science related ideas, ability to solve science related problems as an active citizen

4	Learning in a digital world	Ability to distinguish reliable from unreliable information, effective from ineffective, possess analytical skills
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Surprisingly, there are basic competencies in language teaching, such as speaking, reading, writing and listening. Among them, the ability to listen is assessed as a process that should be carried out not for understanding, but for responding. According to R. Steven, the process of understanding and responding after reasoning is called empathic listening.

Steven's idea can also be applied to the stage of reading comprehension, and we call this process empathic reading. In this case, empathic reading means the ability to read, analyze and apply information to a problem.

Therefore, it is important to develop empathic reading skills in empathic students during reading assignments in native language lessons and during assignments. Psychologist P. Fonagy considers empathy to be a process that we can experience for a person based on the ability to imagine what another person feels [6]. The process of understanding what has been read and feeling through imagination is carried out jointly.

Table 4. Contents of knowledge to be mastered on the basis of science [5]

Text	Personal, collective and common problems requiring understanding, from different periods.
Knowledge	Understanding of basic information, concepts and theories, as well as artefactual, procedural and epistemic knowledge.
Competence	Understanding of phenomena, the ability to conduct scientific research, scientific argumentation, evaluation, critical thinking, decision making, analysis and the ability to use it.
Scientific identification	Perception and awareness of problems

Summary. According to some new generation textbooks, the ratio of practical and theoretical assignments is assessed as mandatory. Of course, grammar has not been abandoned. Only the rules are created on the basis of the practical process and concluded by the students themselves.

According to the international research program prepared by the OECD, studying the content of knowledge gained in the subject when creating a national curriculum and new textbooks on the subject of mother tongue, as well as integration into the content of textbooks, is a targeted method for achieving good results in international studies.

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